

Cross Sectional Study of Histopathologically Confirmed Papulosquamous Skin Disorders at a Tertiary Health Care Centre of HaryanaAbhijit Garg¹, Karandeep Singh², Aman Goyal³, Sneh Kumari⁴¹Postgraduate Resident, Department of Pathology, Maharaja Agrasen Medical College Agroha, Hisar, Haryana²Professor, Department of Pathology, Maharaja Agrasen Medical College Agroha, Hisar, Haryana³Associate Professor, Department of Dermatology, Maharaja Agrasen Medical College Agroha, Hisar, Haryana⁴Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Maharaja Agrasen Medical College Agroha, Hisar, Haryana

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Papulosquamous disorders are a diversified cluster of skin disorders that often poses a diagnostic dilemma to both clinicians and pathologists. In this cross sectional study, 60 consecutive cases of non-infectious erythematous papulosquamous skin disorders which initially presented in skin outpatient department were histopathologically confirmed in pathology department and association of these orders with their age, sex and overall frequency of occurrence was determined.

Result and Conclusion: Out of 60 patients, 40 were male and 20 were female with a ratio of 2:1 and mean age was 37.7 years. Among all papulosquamous disorders psoriasis vulgaris was most common followed by lichen planus.

Keywords: Papulosquamous, Psoriasis Vulgaris, Lichen Planus.

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Introduction

The papulosquamous skin disorders are a big diversified cluster that is examined by clinicians today [1]. The clinical features of papulosquamous disorders overlap with each other's in the way of their morphology and distributional sites which causes difficulty in correctly diagnosing them. Hence these lesions get easily misdiagnosed. [2] The spectrum of non-infectious, erythematous, papulosquamous skin lesions include Lichen Planus, Psoriasis, Prurigo Nodularis, Pityriasis Rosea, Pityriasis Rubra pilaris, Erythema Annulare Centrifugum and many more. [3]

Therefore a histological examination attempt of the lesion should be made to anatomize the histopathologic characteristics of the non-infectious erythematous, papulosquamous lesions of the skin. [4] The histopathological examination is the gold standard method to confirm the diagnosis [5] whereas non-classical presentation of the disease, inappropriate biopsy site, and treatment effect are some of the limitations faced by the histopathologists. [6] In the cluster of papulosquamous skin lesions, it is found that psoriasis and lichen planus are the most common conditions. The prevalence of psoriasis in India is

0.44-2.8% [7] and prevalence of lichen planus is 0.9 -1.8% [8-14] respectively.

Aims and Objectives: To find out the association of papulosquamous skin lesions in patients with their age and sex.

Material and Methods

A hospital based cross sectional study was conducted for 1 year in the Department of Dermatology & Pathology at Maharaja Agrasen Medical College, Agroha (Hisar).

The cases for study comprised of patients with, erythematous, papulosquamous skin disorders which presented in skin outpatient department where lesional punch biopsy was taken and diagnosis was confirmed by histopathological examination of biopsy sample in department of pathology.

The study was done between January 2023 to December 2023. The sample size for study came out to be 60 after following the below inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- All patients with clinical suspicion/diagnosis of non-infectious erythematous papulosquamous skin lesions.
- Adequate biopsy (3-5mm in size).

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients are suggestive of having infectious skin lesions.
- Inadequate biopsy.
- Patients on treatment.

The approval for study was received from institutional scientific and ethical committee.

The data was entered into an excel sheet and analysed with SPSS version 20.0. The quantitative data were expressed in terms of mean and standard deviation while qualitative data were expressed by proportions.

Results

The current study was done on a total of 60 skin biopsied and histopathologically confirmed cases to assess the epidemiological characteristics of non-infectious erythematous papulosquamous lesions. The mean age was 37.7 years. In our study out of 60 patients, 40 (67%) were males and 20 (33%) were females.

Table 1: Sex distribution in Histopathological confirmed skin diseases (n=60)

Diagnosis	Gender	No. of patients	Percentage
Psoriasis and its variants	Female	6	21.4%
	Male	22	78.6%
Lichen Planus and its Variants	Female	11	52.4%
	Male	10	47.6%
Other	Female	3	27.3%
	Male	8	72.7%
Total		60	100%

Above table depicts that, In 28 psoriatic skin patient's males (78.6%) were more affected than females (21.4%) with a ratio of 3.6:1, whereas in lichen planus out of 21 cases, slightly more females (52.4%) were affected than males (47.6%) with a ratio of 1.1:1. In other skin disorders again males (72.7%) were more affected than females (27.31%) with an overall ratio of 2.6:1.

Table 2: Age distribution in histopathologically confirmed skin diseases (n=60)

Scaly skin diseases	Age categories	Number of patients	Percentage
Psoriasis and its variants	<10 years	0	0.0%
	11-20 years	2	7.1%
	21-30 years	7	25.0%
	31-40 years	4	14.3%
	41-50 years	9	32.1%
	51-60 years	3	10.7%
Lichen Planus and its Variants	>60 years	3	10.7%
	<10 years	1	4.8%
	11-20 years	5	23.8%
	21-30 years	4	19.0%
	31-40 years	1	4.8%
	41-50 years	4	19.0%
Others	51-60 years	4	19.0%
	>60 years	2	9.5%
	<10 years	2	18.2%
	11-20 years	2	18.2%
	21-30 years	2	18.2%
	31-40 years	2	18.2%
Total	41-50 years	2	18.2%
	51-60 years	1	9.1%
	>60 years	0	0.0%
	Total	60	100%

Above table shows that out of 60 studied patients, the most (32.1%) of affected patients were in fifth decade and no patient was found in age group less than 10 years in cases of psoriasis vulgaris. In Lichen Planus majority of affected were in second decade (23.8%), while in other skin disease patient category, all age groups were affected with the exception of age group more than 60 years (0.0%)

Table 3: Spectrum of histopathological diagnosis of all papulosquamous skin lesions (n=60)

Histopathological Diagnosis	No. of patients	Percentage
Acrodermatitis continua of hallopeau	2	3.3%
Actinic lichen planus	1	1.7%
Erythema annulare centrifugum	1	1.7%
Erythema dyschromicum perstans	2	3.3%
Hypertrophic lichen planus	3	5%
Lichen nitidus	1	1.7%
Lichen plano pilaris	1	1.7%
Lichen planus	13	21.7%
Lichen planus pemphigoides	1	1.7%
Lichen planus pigmentosus	1	1.7%
Lichen sclerosus	1	1.7%
Lichen simplex chronicus	1	1.7%
Parapsoriasis	1	1.7%
Pityriasis rosea	2	3.3%
Pityriasis rubra pilaris	1	1.7%
Prurigo nodularis	2	3.3%
Psoriasis vulgaris	26	43.3%
Total	60	100%

Above table demonstrate that out of 60 skin biopsies received in department of pathology, maximum number (43.3%) were found consistent with histopathological diagnosis of psoriasis vulgaris.

Lichen Planus was identified as second most common skin disorder with 21.7% of cases. Among

other non-infectious papulosquamous skin disorders most of the histopathological diagnosis were in category of Erythema dyschromicum perstans (3.3%), Pityriasis rosea (3.3%) and Prurigo nodularis (3.3%)

Discussion

Table 4: Gender and age comparison of all included patients in our study with other studies

Studies	Male: female	Age group dominance	Gender dominance
Kesdarisetti et al [5]	0.89:1	31-40	Female dominance
Chavhan et al [4]	2:1	21-40	Male dominance
Kaur et al [3]	1.2:1	21-30	Male dominance
Present study	2:1	41-50	Male dominance

Kesdarisetti et al [5], Chavhan et al [4], Kaur et al [3] showed that the majority of cases were of age group 21-40 years while in contrary in present study majority of cases were of fifth decade(41-50) years. In our study male predominance (2:1) which is in concordance with Chavhan et al [4] and Kaur et al [3]. In contrary to our findings, a study done by Kesdarisetti et al [5] showed female predominance.

Table 5: Histopathological diagnosis-comparison of psoriasis, lichen planus and others in various studies

Studies	Total cases	Psoriasis and its variants	Lichen planus and its variants	Other diagnosis
Kesdarisetti et al [5]	70	34 (48.5%)	15 (21.4%)	21 (30.1%)
Agrawal et al [15]	50	30 (60%)	10 (20%)	10 (20%)
Hosamane et al [6]	70	40 (57.17%)	19 (27.14 %)	11 (15.71%)
Chavhan et al [4]	61	20 (32.78%)	35 (57.37%)	6 (9.83%)
Saritha et al [1]	43	7 (16.27%)	21 (48.8%)	15 (34.88%)
Present study	60	28 (46.67%)	21 (35.0%)	11 (18.33%)

In our study, among all papulosquamous erythematous non-infectious skin disorders, psoriasis vulgaris (46.67%) contributed to the bulk of disease which is in concordance with studies done by Kesdarisetti et al [5], Agrawal et al [15], and Hosamane et al [6] while contrary to our study, studies done by Chavhan et al [4] and Saritha et al [1] showed Lichen planus as the most common disorder.

Conclusion

The clinical symptoms of papulosquamous skin diseases overlap in terms of morphology and distributional sites making it difficult to accurately diagnose them.

Hence these lesions are easily misdiagnosed. So histopathological confirmation is mandatory for treatment. In our study, psoriasis vulgaris followed

by lichen planus constitute the bulk of papulosquamous lesions. These lesions display a definitive male predominance with maximum patients in their fifth decade.

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